

Comparing approaches for new AudioWorklets

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ABSTRACT

AudioWorklets are consolidating as a general platform for running arbitrary audio signal processing code on web browsers. A distinctive feature is the ability to use WebAssembly code instead of JavaScript. While WebAssembly allows using existing DSP code written in C/C++, a relevant question is whether there is an advantage with respect to JavaScript when writing new AudioWorklets. This paper describes several approaches for implementing WebAssembly AudioWorklets, and compares them to plain JavaScript and native implementations.

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of the Web Audio API has increased the attractive of the web as a platform for audio applications. Modelled as a Music-N system [8], one of main limitations of this API was the fixed set of unit generators (*AudioNodes* in the Web Audio API). In initial versions, users were able to code custom DSP algorithms in JavaScript using *ScriptProcessorNode*. This *AudioNode*, however, suffers from numerous problems, mainly because, unlike native *AudioNodes*, it is executed in the main thread along with other browser operations such as graphics or networking, which makes it impossible to create reliable real-time audio processing pipelines.

During the last few years, *AudioWorklets*, the alternative for allowing developers to write their own signal processing code, was slowly developed, and eventually made it into major browsers.

Within a similar time frame, *WebAssembly* has emerged as another innovation in browser APIs, allowing the compilation of native code to a bytecode that is executed by a virtual stack machine. A previous version of the concept exists in the form of *asm.js*, a subset of JavaScript that worked as an assembly language. WebAssembly is now available in most browsers and thus *asm.js* can be considered obsolete.

In the current standard, AudioWorklets can be coded either in JavaScript or WebAssembly. During the last few years, much has been published about porting existing codebases to the web. Given the vast amount of C/C++ audio-

related code available nowadays, the attractive of porting such code via WebAssembly is obvious. However, the advantages of WebAssembly are not necessarily limited to that. WebAssembly is being promoted for AudioWorklets on two main grounds [4]: potential performance improvements, and avoiding JavaScript garbage collection. This paper focuses on several options currently available for creating new AudioWorklets. This includes JavaScript, and C/C++ and AssemblyScript via WebAssembly. The goal is to characterize the "gap" [2] between native and different user-written implementations, taking into account performance, but also ease of use. In this sense, given the myriad of potential techniques, the selection focuses on simple approaches that could be of interest to a wide range of programmers from audio development and web development communities.

The paper is organised as follows: the next section reviews recent literature regarding AudioWorklets and WebAssembly. Section 3 reviews different approaches for writing AudioWorklets, with a focus on readability and ease of use. Section 4 compares the performance of three example AudioWorklets for the different approaches and two browsers. Section 5 discusses the main findings, and Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. RELATED WORK

The Web Audio API, including AudioWorklets, has recently become a W3C recommendation. While implementations of the API have been available for more than a decade, AudioWorklets are a relatively recent development, with implementations starting with Chrome in 2018 and Firefox in 2020. The general mechanism was presented in [5]. A tutorial covering different patterns is available from the Chrome team [4]. A workshop by Mozilla covering WebAssembly worklets was presented at the Web Audio Conference [2]. While the two implementations are still not 100% equal, example code from each of the teams is available from these tutorials.

Some research works have been published about porting existing JavaScript systems from previous web audio implementations based on *ScriptProcessorNode* to AudioWorklets. For example, the port of *genish.js* and *gibberish.js* is described in [13], demonstrating the issues in a use case such as live coding for exchanging data with the audio thread. Several existing C++ music languages and libraries, such as *Csound*, *Maximilian*, *Faust* or *Essentia* have been ported to AudioWorklets, first using *asm.js* [10, 9, 18] and then using WebAssembly [11, 16, 3, 6]. The *Faust* compiler itself is available as a WebAssembly module and thus *Faust* can

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be used to create AudioWorklets in web-based systems, as demonstrated in JSPatcher [12].

Many of the above systems implement some sort of Music-N framework, with a selection of unit generators, and a means to combine them into higher-level abstractions such as instruments or effect processors. For these systems, the AudioWorklet is an excellent platform, enabling music creation and audio processing applications that are available on web browsers. On the other hand, the AudioWorklet is designed to interact with the rest of the API as an AudioNode, which can be connected with other nodes from the API to build higher-level abstractions using JavaScript.

The present work focuses on the latter use case and investigates the different approaches for programming AudioWorklets from scratch. This is, using generic programming language primitives rather than unit generators provided by specialized music languages. Specifically, with respect to WebAssembly, the question is whether it is worth using a low-level language such as C/C++ alongside JavaScript when the goal is not to use an existing codebase.

3. WRITING AUDIOWORKLETS

The main point of AudioWorklets is that they run on the audio thread, so that they are not affected by code running on the main thread. This requires a slightly more complex implementation than what was used for ScriptProcessorNodes. Mainly, one needs to write a script with a processor class that implements the DSP code, then registers it using the *registerProcessor* function, available in *AudioWorkletGlobalScope*. This scope is available for the script when running in the audio thread. The script is typically loaded by using the *addModule* function (available from *AudioContext.audioWorklet*) in the main thread. The DSP code can be written in JavaScript, and may also call WebAssembly code. In the latter case, a WebAssembly module needs to be loaded as well. The main options for the general AudioWorklet mechanism are described in [4].

This section focuses on three languages for writing AudioWorklets: pure JavaScript, WebAssembly compiled from C/C++, and WebAssembly compiled from AssemblyScript. Two cases are considered for WebAssembly AudioWorklets: either a WebAssembly function is called for each audio sample, or it is called for a whole buffer of samples (here, the fixed 128-sample buffer specified by the API for AudioWorklets). The first case may be useful for combining multiple unit generators in one AudioWorklet in JavaScript, while updating the values of parameters at each sample, or for optimizing parts of a single-sample feedback loop. For example this approach is used in some of the examples in Maximilian.¹ The second case reduces the amount of JavaScript code and just handles the AudioWorklet buffer to the WebAssembly code. The memory can be allocated by either the JavaScript runtime or reserved at compilation time, with several options available for getting a pointer to allocated memory.

There are many other options in terms of both programming language and memory management, as mentioned at the end of this section, which are out of the scope of the present study. The following subsections highlight some points of interest in the implementation of these options. The full implementation is available from <https://github.com/g-roma/comparing-audioworklets>.

¹<https://github.com/micknoise/Maximilian>

```

1  const BUF_SIZE = 128;
2
3  class SawProcessor extends AudioWorkletProcessor {
4
5      constructor() {
6          super();
7          this.freq = 0;
8          this.buf = new Float32Array(BUF_SIZE);
9          this.incr = 0;
10         this.phase = 0;
11     }
12
13     static get parameterDescriptors() {
14         return [{
15             name: 'frequency',
16             defaultValue: 440
17         }];
18     }
19
20     polyblep(t, dt){
21         if (t < dt) {
22             t /= dt;
23             return 2*((t - (t*t)/2 - 0.5));
24         }
25         else if (t > 1.0 - dt) {
26             t = (t - 1.0) / dt;
27             return 2*((t * t)/2 + t + 0.5);
28         }
29         else return 0;
30     }
31
32     process (inputs, outputs, parameters) {
33         let out = outputs[0];
34         let buf = this.buf;
35         const freqP = parameters.frequency;
36         let curFreq = freqP[0];
37         for (let i = 0; i < BUF_SIZE; i++) {
38             buf[i] = (2 * this.phase - 1) -
39                 this.polyblep(this.phase, this.incr);
40             if(freqP.length > 1) curFreq = freqP[i];
41             if(curFreq !== this.freq){
42                 this.freq = curFreq;
43                 this.incr = curFreq / sampleRate;
44             }
45             this.phase = (this.phase + this.incr) % 1.0;
46         }
47         for (let i = 0; i < out.length; i++) {
48             out[i].set(buf);
49         }
50         return true;
51     }
52 }
53
54 registerProcessor('saw-js-processor', SawProcessor);

```

Figure 1: Example JavaScript sine oscillator

3.1 Pure JavaScript

JavaScript is of course always present in web development, so one incentive for writing AudioWorklets in JavaScript is not adding yet another language to a web code base. The AudioWorklet implementation actually promotes JavaScript as a first-class citizen.² This is helped by the current speed of JavaScript engines, which has improved over the years. One important drawback of JavaScript for DSP is garbage collection, which can cause unpredictable costs in code. At the same time, for faster code it is often recommended to

²<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=g1L4O1smMC0>

use typed arrays (e.g. `Float32Array`) and traditional *for* loops. This means that JavaScript for DSP code will often emphasize C-like syntax. Figure 1 shows a pure JavaScript AudioWorklet implementing a band-limited sawtooth oscillator using the popular *polyBlep* [15] algorithm. Several assumptions are made that will be held throughout this section: the worklet will only have one output (which is fair for an oscillator), and the buffer size is kept at 128 (as specified by the web audio API). Also, as specified by the API, the parameter may have only one value if no changes are scheduled within the buffer.

```

1 // Binding code (C++ side)
2 EMSCRIPTEN_BINDINGS(SawOsc) {
3   emscripten::class_<SawOsc>("SawOsc")
4     .constructor<double>()
5     .function("process", &SawOsc::process,
6             emscripten::allow_raw_pointers());
7 }

```

```

1 // Processor code (JavaScript side)
2 // in constructor():
3 this._osc = new Module.SawOsc(sampleRate);
4 // in process():
5 buf[i] = this._osc.process(curFreq);

```

Figure 2: Using Embind

3.2 C/C++

C and C++ are well established languages for audio signal processing, and there are plenty of libraries and examples that can be used to program DSP algorithms. Thus, C and C++ are also primary choices for AudioWorklets through WebAssembly. Compilation to WebAssembly is commonly done through Emscripten [17]. We will focus on a C++ approach. For object-oriented code, one challenge is how to expose the functionality across the language barrier. A convenient solution is provided by Embind.³ This feature allows exposing C++ classes and methods and using them in JavaScript in an OOP fashion. An example is shown in Figure 2. Here, the processor of Figure 1 has been modified to use the C++ version (duplicate code is not shown). The C++ code is roughly equivalent to the JavaScript version except that the buffering is still kept in the JavaScript side.

Embind generates a mixture of WebAssembly code and JavaScript glue code, which can be exported to a single js file. This file may be imported as an ES6 module in the processor script, but this feature is still not supported in Firefox. The other option is just to concatenate the processor script with the js file generated by Emscripten, which is then loaded altogether in the `addModule` call.

In this example, the `process` function produces a single sample. Since the AudioWorklet uses a fixed buffer size of 128 samples, a second approach is to generate the whole buffer in the C++ side. An example is shown in Figure 3. Here, the JavaScript code calls `malloc` on the C++ side to allocate the required memory and get the pointer to the start of the buffer. The memory is then mapped to a JavaScript `Float32Array`. The pointer is then passed to the C++ `process`

³https://emscripten.org/docs/porting/connecting_cpp_and_javascript/embind.html

function which just needs to be modified from the previous example to fill the buffer in a loop.

```

1 // Processor code (JavaScript side)
2 // in constructor():
3 this._osc = new Module.SawOsc(sampleRate);
4 this._outputPointer = Module._malloc(BUFFER_SIZE *
5   BYTES_PER_SAMPLE);
6 this.buffer = new Float32Array(
7   Module.asm.memory.buffer,
8   this._outputPointer,
9   BUFFER_SIZE
10 )
11 // in process():
12 this._osc.process(this._outputPointer, curFreq);

```

Figure 3: Using WASM memory

3.3 AssemblyScript

AssemblyScript is a new programming language based on TypeScript, which is a superset of JavaScript. AssemblyScript compiles to WebAssembly, so it can be seen as the best of both worlds. As a JavaScript-like language, it will be familiar to web developers (especially considering the adoption of TypeScript in projects such as Angular, or Tone.js, to cite a web audio example). Also, by focusing on WebAssembly, it clearly documents and exposes all the aspects of this format. At the time of this writing, the latest release is version 0.2, so it can be still considered experimental. Despite this, applications to music have already been demonstrated, notably Peter Salomonsen’s *JavaScript Music* [14]. Like in the case of the C++ libraries discussed above, in this project all the instruments are implemented in the WebAssembly side.

AssemblyScript does not support exposing classes to the JavaScript runtime. However, it maps a JavaScript-like module directly to the WebAssembly module, so exporting a set of functions provides a familiar interface. An example is shown in Figure 4. While some JavaScript code is still needed to handle the buffer and communication with the outside world, this allows the AssemblyScript module to focus on the oscillator algorithm, which requires relatively little code. Again, the interface can be implemented in a sample-based or buffer-based manner. In this example, the pointer was just assumed to start at 0, and an offset is added to the WebAssembly module through a compiler flag, so that the required amount is guaranteed to be available at the beginning of the WebAssembly module memory.

3.4 Other options

Thanks to the adoption of LLVM and to tools such as *Binaryen*, there are many other languages that can be compiled to WebAssembly.⁴ C/C++ and AssemblyScript can be seen as potentially popular options, the former because of its prevalence in audio applications, and the latter because of its proximity to JavaScript. It is also possible to code WebAssembly by hand.

In addition to different languages, there are also other approaches for managing memory that are not considered in this paper. For example, as mentioned in [4], a *SharedArray-*

⁴See e.g. <https://github.com/appcypher/awesome-wasm-languages>

```

1  const BUFFER_SIZE = 128;
2  let phase:f32 = 0;
3  let frequency:f32 = 0;
4  let incr:f32 = 0;
5  let sampleRate:f32 = 0;
6
7  export function init(_sampleRate:f32):void{
8    sampleRate = _sampleRate;
9  }
10
11 function polyBlep(t:f32, dt:f32):f32{
12   if (t < dt) {
13     t /= dt;
14     return t + t - t * t - 1.0;
15   }
16   else if (t > 1.0 - dt) {
17     t = (t - 1.0) / dt;
18     return t * t + t + t + 1.0;
19   }
20   else return 0;
21 }
22
23 export function process (freq:f32):void {
24   if(frequency!=freq){
25     incr = freq / sampleRate;
26     frequency = freq;
27   }
28   for(let i:i32 = 0; i < BUFFER_SIZE; i++){
29     store<f32>(i <<2, (2 * phase - 1) - polyBlep(phase,
30       incr));
31     phase = Mathf.mod(phase + incr, 1.);
32   }
}

```

Figure 4: AssemblyScript version

Buffer may allow for more flexible configurations of threads while avoiding asynchronous messaging. However, due to security issues, this technology was temporarily removed from browsers and is not yet universally available.

4. PERFORMANCE COMPARISON

Given that audio runs in real-time, performance of unit generators is traditionally an important concern. This section compares the performance of the described approaches to creating AudioWorklets from a user point of view.

4.1 Experiment

In order to characterize the difference in performance of the different approaches, the sawtooth oscillator of Section 3 was implemented in several variants: JavaScript, C++ (per-sample and buffer-based) and AssemblyScript (per-sample and buffer-based). Since native oscillators available in the web audio API are generally implemented using wavetables, this example is meant to illustrate the implementation of a new AudioWorklet using a different algorithm. In order to provide a point of comparison with native AudioNodes, two more basic examples were implemented. First, given that the Sine oscillator is implemented using the *sin* function in Firefox [1], the simplest possible oscillator was implemented in this way. In addition, a low-pass biquad filter based on the Firefox implementation of *BiquadFilterNode* was implemented. In general, the implementations are not expected to result the fastest possible code for each platform, as optimization is a never-ending game. The point is to reflect on the differences

Figure 5: Maximum number of worklets for each approach and browser for the Sawtooth worklet

between variants both from the point of view of performance and ease of use.

The experiment was designed to measure performance from a user point of view: instead of the load in the system or the number of function calls, we ask how many worklets we would be able to create before the audio starts glitching. A reference oscillator is played and used to determine the breakout point, while worklets are created in the background at zero or near-zero gain. A difficulty of the procedure is that random glitches may appear due to instantiation or (even with AudioWorklets) user actions such as switching applications. In order to make the comparison as objective as possible, the oscillators are instantiated progressively using a *setInterval* call, and the maximum number is approximated to be the last value before the reference oscillator is consistently distorted. The test was quantised to steps of 50 worklets.

The experiment was run on a M1 Pro 2021 MacBook pro using Firefox 99 and Chrome 100. All WebAssembly versions were compiled using level 3 optimization. For the AssemblyScript version, the Math library was mapped to the 32bit *NativeMathf*.⁵ However, for the Sine oscillator, this proved to be significantly slow, so for the *sin* function, instead of the stock version, the approach in JavaScript Music was used.⁶

4.2 Results

Figure 5 shows the maximum number of oscillators for the polyBlep sawtooth oscillator. Figure 6 shows the result for the Sine oscillator, and Figure 7 for the low-pass filter.

While many of the results may depend on implementation details and specific optimizations, some patterns are easily observed with respect to the relative performance of each approach.

With respect to the comparison between JavaScript and other implementations, there are striking differences between platforms. While Chrome seems to favour the performance of native AudioNodes, in Firefox the JavaScript implementations approach the native ones. In the case of the Sine oscillator, this may be due to the fact that, unlike Firefox,

⁵<https://www.assemblyscript.org/stdlib/math.html>

⁶<https://github.com/petersalomonson/javascriptmusic/issues/2#issuecomment-469419609>

Figure 6: Maximum number of worklets for each approach and browser for the Sine worklet

Figure 7: Maximum number of worklets for each approach and browser for the low-pass filter worklet

the Chrome implementation uses a wavetable instead of a *sin* function. Also, as noted, the AssemblyScript version performance was improved by changing the *sin* implementation, so it can be concluded that this function has a strong effect on the comparison for the Sine oscillator.

A second interesting result is that, especially in Firefox, the pure JS version stands well against WebAssembly implementations. This may be surprising, although it is in line with previous results comparing WebAssembly to JavaScript [7]. This seems to indicate that JavaScript still holds promise for AudioWorklets, provided that garbage collection is avoided.

With respect to the per-sample vs buffer-based approaches, the buffer versions are always faster. This could be expected, as there is likely a non-negligible cost in each call to a WebAssembly function. Thus, this cost should be balanced with the potential gains in moving a certain function to WebAssembly as opposed to implementing it in JavaScript.

Finally, with respect to AssemblyScript, the results are mixed, although in most cases they don't seem to reach the performance of the JavaScript and the Emscripten implementations for the buffer-based case. Overall, Emscripten / C++ using a buffer seems to be the safest bet for WebAssembly, with respect to performance.

5. DISCUSSION

The aim of the implementations and experiment described in this paper was to reflect on the question of whether it is worth using WebAssembly for new AudioWorklets when no previous codebase is used. The answer will obviously depend on many factors in any concrete situation. Nevertheless, the results can help understanding the tradeoffs incurred when using WebAssembly in AudioWorklets.

One clear tradeoff is the cost of communication between JavaScript and WebAssembly code. This must be accounted both in terms of performance and implementation complexity. With respect to the former, the cost of calling WebAssembly code must be assessed in terms of granularity. With respect to the latter, involving WebAssembly in the development of AudioWorklets incurs a significant cost: first, it still requires a significant amount of JavaScript code, second, it requires using a second language and toolchain, and handling the problem of loading external code into the audio thread. Hopefully, these difficulties will be eased in the future as implementations settle and new abstractions are developed. However, in its current shape, the API seems to promote growing codebases at either side of the divide, rather than using WebAssembly to create many AudioNodes that are used along with native ones.

Regardless of the cost of communication, a second tradeoff is the choice of language. In terms of performance, the results seem to be discouraging for the use of WebAssembly with respect to JavaScript. This may be attributed to the time and energy that has been devoted to JavaScript engines. In any case, a clear advantage of using WebAssembly is the possibility of using different languages. As seen in the AssemblyScript example, this may allow concise implementations DSP algorithms, although, again, this is at the expense of writing some JavaScript code to handle the communication. Finally, it is worth noting that WebAssembly does not support garbage collection. Since garbage collection cannot be disabled in JavaScript, this is a clear advantage of WebAssembly for implementing DSP code.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The availability of WebAssembly and AudioWorklets have significantly improved the possibilities of the Web audio API as a generic audio development platform. Given the potential of WebAssembly for creating efficient and predictable code, one relevant question is whether it is worth the added complexity and use of an extra language for writing new AudioWorklets. While the answer to this question will always depend on specific factors, this paper has contributed some examples to characterise the tradeoffs.

With respect to the code, JavaScript, C++ and AssemblyScript have a relatively similar syntax, particularly with respect to writing signal processing code. AssemblyScript seems to strike a promising balance between conciseness and predictability. On the other hand, using WebAssembly still involves writing significant amounts of JavaScript.

With respect to performance, the proposed experiment shows that the possibility of partially closing the "gap" between native and user-written audio nodes is not unthinkable, even if using plain JavaScript. WebAssembly is clearly not a magic bullet that makes code automatically faster, but it provides more tools for creating efficient signal processing code. As the AudioWorklet implementations are relatively young, there may be room for improvement for both JavaScript and WebAssembly. Regardless, given the potential of pure JavaScript AudioWorklets, an interesting avenue would be to further investigate and document the main pitfalls of JavaScript for audio signal processing.

Several limitations of this study, particularly with respect to performance, are left for future work. The experiment was run on a single hardware / OS combination. Even so, there were major differences between browsers. Thus, when considering other platforms, including e.g. mobile phones, it is possible that the differences between WebAssembly and JavaScript become less relevant. With respect to different ways to generate WebAssembly, another interesting direction for the future would be to compare the code generated by different languages and compilers. This could in turn help including more languages in the comparison, which is a promising affordance of WebAssembly for finding a good balance between usability and performance in audio programming.

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